

SAGROPIA – Sustainable agriculture through novel pesticides using an integrated approach

Deliverable 7.2 DMP-Data Management Plan Version 1

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1 Publishable Summary

This deliverable 7.2. “Data Management Plan” defines the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the Sagropia project. Throughout the course of the project, the DMP will be cured and updated. The DMP will be released three times, i.e. in M6, M30, and M60 (at the end of the project).

The DMP covers the following aspects:

- The responsibility for the custody of data.
- The types of data collected in the project.
- The standards to be followed for data collection and preservation, including the compliance of data standards of the GAIA-X ecosystem and of data usage in the International Space for Agriculture (IDSA).
- The data access and re-use policies.
- The basic principles for data sharing with future stakeholders.
- The security measures, intellectual property, privacy, and confidentiality of the data.
- The archiving and preservation of data.

Disclaimer: The document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including its associated Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

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2 Introduction

Sagropia operates at the interface of crop production, pest and disease control, EU legislation and product regulation, and day to day farming practice. Aiming at replacing several ‘candidates for substitution’ active substances or reducing their overall use, Sagropia will offer new biocontrol solutions that are being formulated, with production being upscaled, and their mode of action being studied. However, Sagropia envisions not simple replacement of chemical pesticides, but will incorporate its solutions into innovative, comprehensive IPM strategies that will be demonstrated in participatory real life-trials with active participation and engagement of farmers.

Project activities and major findings will be communicated, and results generated will be disseminated to reach a wide range of actors and stakeholders in the action areas concerned, thus strengthening the uptake of innovation and supporting key policy priorities. Through the generation, collection, and publication of research data, as well as their sharing with the wider research community, we will promote and effectively validate Sagropia’s research results. Therefore, working under open science practices is a key strategy to make project outcomes widely available. This document describes the Data Management Plan (DMP) for Sagropia, dealing with multiple concerns about the treatment of project data, including use in publications and exploitation of research findings.

The DMP is regularly updated to include newly generated data content during the project lifetime.

2.1 Definitions

Data set	Digital information created during scientific research, but which is not a published research output. Research data excludes purely administrative records. Research data do not include publications, articles, lectures, or presentations.
Data Management Plan	A formal working document which outlines how data sets will be handled both during the active research phase and after the project is completed.
Metadata	Information about data sets stored in a repository/database template. For example, an image may require metadata that describes how large the picture is, the color depth, the image resolution, when the image was created, and other data. A text document's metadata may contain information about how long the document is, who the author is, when the document was written, and a short summary of the document.
Secondary data	Sources that contain commentary on or a discussion about a primary source.
Zenodo	Research output publication and archival service built and developed by researchers from the CERN IT department, to ensure that everyone can join in Open Science. Based on the open source Invenio digital library framework, Zenodo was created through the OpenAIRE project and is hosted at CERN (https://giving.web.cern.ch/content/zenodo-0).

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3 Measures for Data Management

3.1 Data Management Plan as a Living Document

The data management plan (DMP) will be kept in place throughout the entire project lifetime and will be accessible to all beneficiaries via the project file sharing system. The DMP will be regularly updated and saved together with related data. We will create three main versions of the DMP:

- 1st version at M6, being part of this deliverable.
- 2nd version at M30, being deliverable D7.3.
- Final version at M60 at the end of the project (Deliverable D7.4).

The DMP addresses a number of issues that are critical to data management processes, such as:

- Data summary
- FAIR data
- Research outputs
- Allocation of resources
- Data security
- Ethics

The Sagropia consortium takes measures to ensure high-quality data management. Most important, during regular consortium meetings, we assess the status of the DMP, and assess the dissemination of data and their potential publication. AIT as the scientific coordinator will assist researchers in the project to prepare the data according to project needs as well as following the FAIR principles.

3.2 Dissemination and Exploitation of Data

Owners of research datasets resulting from project work are required to develop and implement a dissemination and exploitation strategy for such data. Here, it is important to understand that the obligation to exploit results does not replace the obligation to disseminate results, and vice versa. Art. 16 of the GA stipulates that exploitation strategies may refer to post-project Research & Development (R&D) activities, the use of research data for the development and commercialization of products and services, and/or in standardisation activities. Therefore, Sagropia partners need to balance open access & open data requirements with potential exploitation opportunities, in particular commercial ones. Thus, all datasets will be first checked for their exploitation potential before dissemination. Data underlying scientific publications will be made available without restrictions. For all other datasets, it will be decided on a case-by-case basis whether access can be granted without giving away sensitive information. For example, data whose release would limit the patentability of a result, will not be made accessible to the public. In general, access will be as open as possible, but as restricted as necessary.

The commercial potential of expected Sagropia results has already been addressed in the proposal that has been turned into the DoA. Consequently, it is crucial that post-project use of generated research datasets contributes to the further development and delivery of partners' exploitation plans.

Along these lines, project partners may also request access rights to the owner of resulting research datasets under fair and reasonable conditions, whenever it is needed for the development and implementation of their exploitation plans. This is stipulated in Art. 9.4.1 of the Sagropia CA: Access rights to results if needed for exploitation of a party's own results shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions. Access rights to results for internal research and for teaching activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

According to Art. 17 of the GA, the research data generated in Sagropia must be disseminated as soon as possible and by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific

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publications (in any medium). Such means and conditions of the dissemination activities fall under the responsibility of the owner of the resulting research dataset. The GA has also established the obligation to share research data (and metadata) underlying (peer-reviewed) scientific publications, in Art. 17.4 on open access publications:

Sagropia partners agreed during proposal development to adhere to Open Science principles with regard to research data generated (as result) in the project. All legal requirements are described in Art. 17 of the GA (Open science: research data management). The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:

- establish a data management plan ('DMP') (and regularly update it)
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or
 - be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP- this will be added in more detail in the data register with the next deliverable update.
- provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

3.3 Intellectual Property and Rights

The balance between the project's openness and confidentiality requirements for research data generated within the project will be discussed on a case-by-case basis by project partners. It is, however, evident that, whenever a generated research dataset has potential commercial or industrial value, the owner of such a dataset must take all pertinent measures to protect it, in line with the obligations of the Grant Agreement (GA). Specifically, Art. 16 of the GA details the obligation to protect results:

"Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results — for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage — if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other beneficiaries and any other legitimate interests."

A research dataset is any organised collection of data defined by a theme or category that reflects what is being measured, observed, or monitored. In this regard, an original research dataset may be protected in Europe by Copyright Law. This means that the developer of such a dataset may claim an exclusive right for 70 years (this duration can differ in non-EU countries) to exclude others from using, copying, and exploiting this dataset without prior given consent.

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Also, partners may claim the *sui generis* right for the protection of original databases for a period of 15 years. The *sui generis* database right protects a database, which is defined as follows in Article 1 (2) of the EU Database Directive (96/9/EC):

"[...] a collection of independent works, data or other materials arranged in a systematic or methodical way and individually accessible by electronic or other means." (DIRECTIVE 96/9/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL (March 1996) on the legal protection of databases. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A31996L0009>)

Furthermore, research datasets generated by partners within the project can also be marked as "Confidential Information" according to Section 10 of the CA, with the purpose to limit access for disclosure outside of the consortium. Such restriction applies not only for the duration of project implementation, but also for a period of 5 years after the project has ended.

Taking all this into consideration, all partners are highly encouraged to mark their data as confidential whenever it might be needed for the implementation of their exploitation strategies.

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4 The Sagropia Data Management Plan

All data, including text documents, data sets, sequence data, etc., used (existing or generated) within Sagropia will be documented using the **data register file** template provided in the Annex of the deliverable document.

The **data register file** contains descriptive information of the data it represents, giving a precise data report that follows the instructions given by the Horizon Europe DMP template [HEDMP21], covering the aspects described in this section.

4.1 Data Summary

The data used in the course of the Sagropia project will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be analysed from a range of methodological perspectives for project development and scientific purposes. Whenever possible, respecting IPRs and the consortium agreement, these data sets will be available in a variety of easily accessible formats, including Post Script (PDF, XPS), Power Point (PPTX, PPT), image (JPEG, PNG, GIF, TIFF), compressed formats (TAR.GZ, MTZ), packet traces (PCAP), HTML, etc.

A data summary is provided for all Sagropia datasets through the **data register file**, covering the following points:

- **Name:** Descriptive and unique identifier.
- **Description of dataset (content):** What kind of data is included in this data set?
- **Owner:** Beneficiary/ beneficiaries generating the dataset or contributing to its generation.
- **Source (origin):** What is the provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
Prior data: is the data being re-used from an existing data set? for what purpose? In case prior data is available, but its re-use is discarded, what are the reasons for that?
- **Types, formats, and expected size:** What types, formats, and expected size of data will the project generate or re-use?
- **Storing & Access issues:** What are the data storage provisions?
- **Exploitation & Dissemination (addressing the significance to the project):** What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project? This refers also to **utility aspects:** To whom might the data be useful outside the project?

4.2 FAIR Principle

The Sagropia data, including publications, experimental data, and other data sets, is published to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Since the open-access repository Zenodo is widely used in the scientific community, it will be used for all open data generated in the project. Zenodo.org is open, free, searchable, and structured with flexible licensing allowing for storing all types of data: data sets, images, presentations, publications, and software. In addition, Zenodo allows researchers to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them.

4.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

According to the FAIR principles, data must be assigned a unique persistent identifier, be described with rich metadata, and be registered or indexed in a searchable resource to be findable.

In the Sagropia project, data will either be published directly with a persistent identifier (DOI), in repositories/databases providing UIDs) or along a scientific publication (with DOI), e.g. in the supporting material or with link to an open archive.

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We foresee for the different types of research data during the project:

- Experimental (raw) data: direct publication of the data set (with DOI) or deposition into a public repository providing unique identifier (e.g. sequence accession numbers)
- Processed experimental data: published in scientific articles.
- Numerical data: direct publication of the data set (with DOI)

A Sagropia Zenodo channel has been opened to disseminate the data sets generated in the project (<https://zenodo.org/communities/sagropia/?page=1&size=20>).

For those data sets that the consortium decides for open access, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned and linked to the object in Zenodo. This DOI can be used in any relevant publications to direct readers to the underlying data set. Search keywords will be provided when the data set is uploaded to Zenodo, which will optimize possibilities for re-use, following the minimum DataCite Metadata Schema standards, containing the fields listed in Table 1, which are also included in the data register file (Annex 1). There, each data set generated during the project will be recorded with the fields in Table 2 that are marked with an *. The owner of each data set will be responsible for the creation of a new entry in the register associated with the generated data set and notify AIT (data manager).

Newly created data sets will be provided with rich metadata. As a consortium project with research groups from various disciplines, we expect various different kinds of data. As far as metadata standards exist for the project related disciplines, we will make use of them.

For example, for sequencing data, we will follow the metadata standards of the NCBI repositories NCBI Genbank and NCBI SRA as these are the standard discipline archives/repositories/databases for depositing nucleotide sequences and raw sequencing data. NCBI uses the metadata standard "BioSample Data Model" to store metadata associated with biological samples. The BioSample Data Model is a standardised format for describing biological samples and their associated metadata, including sample identifiers, organism names, sample attributes, and other relevant information. BioSample Data Model is compatible with other metadata standards, such MIGS/MIMS (Minimum Information about a Genome Sequence/Minimum Information about a Metagenome Sequence).

The metadata for our datasets will comply with the "Datacite v4" and "Dublin Core" metadata standards and will be offered in file formats (.xml, .json) that can be harvested and indexed. Zenodo, which will be used as a main repository of our project, facilitates any metadata harvesting and indexing with the use of the OAI-PMH protocol (Open Archives Initiative's Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) and its own REST API.

Table 1– Structure of the meta-information record for each generated data set

DATA DENOMINATION	
Data set reference name *	The reference name will start with the prefix "DS_PATH2DEA" indicating it's a data set
Data set title *	The title of the data set which should be easily searchable and findable
Description	A brief description of the data set
Keywords	The keywords associated with the data set
Version Number *	To keep track of changes to the data sets
DATA ORIGIN	
Name(s) of data set creator(s) *	Lead partners responsible for the creation of the data set, and their affiliation
Data Source	How/why was the data set generated/re-used
Creation Date *	Date of generation of the data set
Quality Assurance	Brief description of the quality assurance processes the data has gone through
DATA SPECIFICATIONS	
Type *	Type of data contained in the data set
Format *	This could be CSV, PCAP, HTML, etc.
Expected Size *	The approximate size of the data set

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DATA ACCESSIBILITY	
Data Location *	The repository where the data are stored: partner owned, VRE, PATH2DEA OR, Zenodo
Date of Repository Submission *	The date of submission to the repository can be added once it has been submitted
Digital Object Identifier *	The DOI can be entered once the data set has been deposited in the repository
Access Status *	Whether a data set is “open”, “consortium” or “restricted”
Embargo Period *	Duration of embargo foreseen for a data set
Funding statement	A disclaimer indicating that the specific data set was generated within the PATH2DEA project that received funding from the UE
DATA UTILITY	
Significance to the project *	The associated work package this data set originates from
Significance outside the project	To whom the data might be useful outside the project
DATA PUBLICATIONS	
Related Publications	Bibliographical details of publications based on the data set
Data set Citation	A ‘ready-to-use’ citation reference for the data set

4.2.1 Making data accessible

According to the FAIR principles, (meta)data are accessible if they can always be obtained by machines and humans. This is achieved when appropriate authorization is given, a well-defined protocol is in place, and access to metadata is provided, even when the data are not or no longer available.

The research data created in Sagropia is owned by the partner that generates it. Each partner is responsible for their dissemination unless there is legitimate interest to protect it. A partner that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other partners (grant agreement provisions apply), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

The data will be made accessible following the accessibility criteria:

Restricted data:

accessible by the owner only, deposited in the repository of the owner partner. Data must be kept for at least 5 years after the project ends.

Consortium data:

accessible by the consortium members only, deposited in the repository of the owner partner. Data must be kept for at least 5 years after the project ends.

Open data:

accessible by the public, deposited in the Zenodo repository. After the project finalization, data is kept for the lifetime of Zenodo¹, currently 20 years.

If necessary, embargo periods of up to 6 months for specific data sets can be requested by the partner owner of the data, to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property. In such cases, the data will be published on Zenodo with an embargo date¹ after which the data will automatically be made available.

During embargo periods, information about the restricted data will be published in the metadata file (Table 1). Where a restriction on open access to data is necessary, attempts will be made to make data available under controlled conditions to other individual researchers.

¹ <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

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4.2.2 Making Data Inter-operable

According to the FAIR principles, (meta)data are interoperable when they use a shared and broadly applicable ontologies or vocabularies, vocabularies that follow FAIR principles, and it includes qualified references to other (meta)data.

The data generated in Sagropia will be documented in a structured and standardized way, to ensure that the data sets can be understood and interpreted with the metadata information. The data sets in Sagropia originating from survey / interviews or other stakeholder interactions (e.g. as indicated in WP4, include roundtables with growers and farmers) will be digitalized in an organized way and stored in an easy-to-use format such as .csv, or .xls files.

When the project demands that specific ontologies or vocabularies are used, they will be published as open data to facilitate its reuse, refining or extension.

4.2.3 Increase Data Re-use

According to the FAIR principles, (meta)data is re-usable when provided with accurate and relevant attributes, a data usage license, information with regards to provenance, and meet domain-relevant community standards.

The data generated in the project will be made available as Open Data to permit the widest re-use possible. Project partners can request exceptions from this rule for commercial, ethical, legal or security reasons. In addition, project partners can also request data publishing embargo, e.g., to maximize the scientific impacts of the project or prepare exploitation measures.

For data that can be publicly released, open licenses such as CC BY or CCO will be used. We expect most of the data to be freely available in the public domain (open-access repositories) to allow re-use. We will only restrict data if it would in particular be against any partner's legitimate interests, including its commercial exploitation. Details on restricted data are outlined above (Section 4.2.1).

Licences for data sharing and re-use remain subject to the project partners who produced the data. Data licensing will be arranged in accordance with the Grant Agreement following e.g. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons. We will use metadata community standards, which will enable users to access the data and increase its findability.

The open data will be made available in Zenodo, as described earlier. To facilitate data re-use and data analysis validation, documentation about data sources, used methodologies, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurements, etc., will be provided for each data set.

If data sets are updated, the partner that possesses the data has the responsibility to manage the different versions and to make sure that the latest version is available in the case of publicly available data. The quality control of the data is the responsibility of the partner owner of the data, and the quality assurance processes will be documented in the data register file (Annex 1) linked to the relevant deliverable.

4.3 Other Research Outputs

Other research outputs, such as software, workflows, protocols, models, reports, presentations, and publications will be managed in the same way as data. Depending on the content and accessibility rights, it will be published in Zenodo.

The principles outlined in the DMP for research data will similarly be applied to digital research output (not being data), such as:

- protocols: expected results are the "Handbook for sampling and sample treatment"
- software: expected results include bioinformatic pipelines and potentially phenotyping pipelines

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- model :are expected in WP5 for sustainability, and life cycle assessments.
- workflows: expected results are IPM concepts.

Physical research output that we expect in Sagropia includes:

- physical samples, such as soil samples, plant samples, RNA
- laboratory samples, such as formulations and components thereof

Potentially identified novel strains that are active biocontrol agents will be publicly deposited in the AIT microbial strain collection. Internet links between the culture collection catalogue and the genome database and the genome sequences will be provided.

4.4 Allocation of Resources

The cost of data publication will be covered by the money granted to the project and assigned to cover publication fees. The same holds for the cost specified on hardware, software and personnel to support sharing and preservation of the data.

All project partners will be involved in the data management. However, AIT will be the responsible consortium partner for the implementation of the DMP. All the consortium partners will also undertake to support the data management protocol by providing the types of generated data that have been described in the methodology. In more detail, AIT will:

- prepare the DMP,
- ensure its update during the project implementation,
- ensure the recording of the produced datasets,
- have the overall responsibility for the implementation of the DMP.

Each Sagropia partner should respect the policies set out in this DMP. Data sets must be created, managed, and stored appropriately and in line with local legislation. Data set validation and registration of metadata and backing up data for sharing through repositories is the responsibility of the partner that generates the data.

Once new data is generated, the data owner must fill the data register file (Annex 1), which should be supervised by the leader of the WP/Task the data is related to before informing the DMP leader (AIT). The data register file will be included in the DMP Deliverable (M6, M30, M60).

Table 2 – Data responsibilities summarizes the responsibilities associated to the data in Sagropia.

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Table 2 – Data responsibilities

Task	Generate data and provide data register input	Supervise metadata file	Publish data in Zenodo	Publish data on Sagropia Website	Supervise the DMP
Responsible	Data owner	WP leader	All WPs	WP 6	DMP leader
Data					
Type	data sets, surveys, audio-visuals, tables, test results, protocols, software tools, etc.		publications, open data sets, open deliverables, software tools	Open reports/ deliverables, dissemination material	All data
Meta data					
Storage					

We will ensure long term preservation of research data by publishing it on trusted and long-time operating repositories. As a consortium we agree to use Zenodo (multi-purpose repository) and NCBI (domain specific repository) as both provide different advantages in use (see above). If unforeseen circumstances require partners to publish in other repositories, this will be discussed in the data management subgroup.

For Zenodo a project community has already been established. This allows all project partners to publish and deposit data without data size restriction. For both Zenodo and NCBI, we therefore do not expect any additional costs for the publication and long time preservation.

Before each research publication, a selection will be made with regard to which data is useful for long-time preservation. The published datasets will be linked with the according publication and will be given a persistent identifier e.g. DOI. A data selection will be made based on reproducibility and re-use purposes. In Sagropia, we have agreed on following specific guidelines for each data publication during project runtime:

- **Raw and processed data**
 - The data in the Zenodo repository will be preserved for the lifetime of the repository. As stated by Zenodo on their "retention period": Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least. (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>)
 - The data deposited to NCBI or ENA will be preserved for the lifetime of the repository/archive. As stated by ENA "All database records submitted to the INSDC [International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, including NCBI Genbank and ENA] will remain permanently accessible as part of the scientific record." (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/about/policies>)
- **Physical samples** will be stored in the storage of the sampling partner and/or the partner performing the analysis of the data.
- **Bacterial strains** (potentially identified and isolated within the project) will be publicly deposited in the AIT Strain Collection and will also be preserved indefinitely, if applicable.
- **Digital research output** will be published on Zenodo following the preservation specifics as outlined above.

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4.5 Data Security

Produced or processed research data (during the production process, i.e. premature to publication) from this project will be securely stored by all project partners in individual storage facility solutions, such

- cloud solutions
- institutional repositories
- institutional servers/databases

All the partners using cloud solutions have special agreements with providers on privacy and information security legislation and guidelines to comply with the GDPR, e.g. storage of data on European servers.

All institutional storage solutions employed in Sagropia are part of the University/company infrastructure and comply with privacy and security policies of the concerning institutes. These facilities allow storage of large data volumes that are backed up on a daily basis, in specialised data centres, not only ensuring the preservation of the data in a trustworthy and dependable location, but also effectively minimising the risk of data loss in the event of any system malfunction or crash.

AIT provides all consortium partners with access to a MS-Teams channel right from the project start, which is regularly backed up. The MS-Teams channel is managed by AIT, and it serves as a communication tool for internal notifications and document sharing, with an attached and dedicated data repository for each WP. After project finalization, AIT will keep all project data for at least 5 years.

All consortium partners are in full compliance with current security standards in terms of data security, backups, anti-virus scans, etc. The servers, on which the data files will be stored are password protected. The passwords are unique, contain more than eight symbols and do not contain any personal information. Only staff working directly on this project will have access to the files containing personal data of the research subjects. The computers and files are password protected.

Sensitive data should be managed by its respective owners and should never be uploaded to the shared project data space. The use of secure institutional systems can provide assurance against any unanticipated attempts at data tampering, whether deliberate or accidental in nature

4.6 Ethics

The Sagropia partners are to comply with the ethical principles, meaning that all activities must be carried out in compliance with:

1. ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity and including avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct)
2. applicable international and national law

We do not see any ethical issues related to the data to be handled in the project. All data providing partners will be requested to communicate to the Data Manager and Project Coordinator if they encounter ethically questionable material or personal data that needs to be handled in the project. As per submission date of the first version of the DMP (M6), none has been detected or filed. If further measures to ensure compliance to ethical and legal standards (e.g., terms of use, compliance agreements with the data providers) are needed, they will be included in the updated versions of the DMP (M30, M60).

As in Sagropia we do not plan to conduct any surveys involving the use of questionnaires dealing with personal data, there are no measures needed related to obtaining informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation of such data.

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4.7 Other Issues

As of the publication date of this deliverable, it is not foreseen to make use of other national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental procedures for data management.

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5 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the data management plan of Sagropia and serves as a guideline for all partners in the consortium who produce or re-use data in the scope of the project. It describes in detail how to treat, store, publish, and document the data sets ensuring the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles. The data management plan follows the directives given by the European Commission and provides a template for the generation of a metadata file per data set, a definition of where data is publishable and their accessibility rights, and a clear designation about data responsibilities for the partner using the data sets and for the data manager. The data management plan is a working document, and it will be updated during the lifetime of the project and its status will be published in M6, M30 and M60 as deliverable D7.2. and updates.

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6 Activity Plan for Data Management

Task	Activities	Resp.	By when / Status
T7.4 Data management (M1-M60), AIT Contributors: All	Develop a data management plan in collaboration with all consortium members	AIT, all	June 24 (M6)
	Setup of data file templates (collaborative)	AIT, all	M3 done
	Setup a central database as platform for the data exchange	AIT, all	M3-4 started
	Data Management plan update	AIT, all	M26
	Final Data Management plan	AIT, all	M54

Deliverables:

D7.2 DMP- Data Management Plan M6-AIT

D7.3 DMP mid-project- M30- AIT

D7.4 DMP — DMP Final -M60- AIT

Milestones:

None in P1

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7 References

[HEDMP21]: EU Grants: Data Management Template (HE):V1.0 – 05.05.2021, <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>, accessed: 05.05.2023

8 Annex 1

Table of produced data

Produced data will be listed with all necessary information in the data register file, named Sagropia_DMP_Data_register_VX.docx (where the VX stands for version number X). The file will be regularly updated and given a new version number. The file is available to all consortium members in the Sagropia file sharing system. The template, at the time of deliverable submission, has the form shown below.

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Annex 1: SAGROPIA Data Register

Dataset name (related deliverable)	Description of dataset Please indicate whether re-used or generated. Also, it would be very useful to indicate when (eg in which month) the dataset is expected to be generated. Or splitting this table per Periods.	Owner	Source(s)	Format & Size	Storing/ Access issues	Dissemination	Exploitation
WP1							
Internal recommendations for PPPs	MoA, PPP application recommendations including some of the internal data (efficacy trials)	CER	Internal knowledge of the products. Data from previous trials with the stand-alone solutions	.ppt, communication (emails, test design protocols)	Server AIT; stored 5 years post project	No dissemination of internal information	Only within the members of the SAGROPIA grant for the purpose of designing and executing trials.
Recommendations on some of the solutions and efficacy	Internal data of OAEU solutions. Prevision on the MoA.	OAEU	Internal knowledge of the products. Data from previous trials with the stand-alone solutions		Server AIT; stored 5 years post project		Basis for further development, data for regulatory approvals and product improvement

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<p>Replacement solutions (D1.1)</p>	<p>List of pesticide solutions including data describing their potential for replacing CfS. These include (a.o); plant growth indicators (biomass), multiplication rates, pathogen population build up; diseases index indicators. The data will be fully available starting from September – December (2024). All data under this category will be generated.</p>	<p>WR</p>	<p>Pot experiments carried out in climate-controlled greenhouses.</p>	<p>Text file and associated Excel spreadsheets. Besides, high-quality pictures describing the effect of SAGROPIA solutions on diseases and pests.</p>	<p>Will be arranged through WR-IT services in our one drive.</p>	<p>Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications</p>	<p>Procedure will be followed as stated in the grant agreement.</p>
<p>Fungal replacement solutions (D1.1)</p>	<p>List of fungicide solutions including plant phenotype data describing their potential for replacing CfS</p>	<p>AIT</p>	<p>Desk analysis and lab testing</p>	<p>Image data; text file and associated Excel spreadsheets</p>	<p>Server AIT; stored 5 years post project</p>	<p>To be defined by M30- in D7.3</p>	<p>Basis for further development, data for regulatory approvals and product improvement To be further defined by M30- in D7.3</p>

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Solution synergies (D1.2)	List of pesticide solutions including data describing their potential for replacing CFS. These include (a.o); plant growth indicators, multiplication rates, pathogen population build up; diseases index indicators. The data will be fully available starting from September – December (2024). All data under this category will be generated.	WR	Pot experiments carried out in climate-controlled greenhouses.	Text file and associated Excel spreadsheets. Besides, high-quality pictures describing the effect of SAGROPIA solutions (combined) on diseases and pests.	Will be arranged through WR-IT services in our one drive.	Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications	Procedure will be followed as stated in the grant agreement.
Fungal synergy replacement solutions (D1.2)	Synergistic effects of fungicide solutions including plant phenotype data describing their potential for replacing CFS	AIT	lab testing	Image data; text file and associated Excel spreadsheets	Server AIT; stored 5 years post project	Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications	Basis for further development, data for regulatory approvals and product improvement To be further defined on detail after M12
WP2							
Upscale protocols (D2.1)	Protocols for upscaled production and formulation of SAGROPIA solutions	OAEU	Desk work	Text files (instructions/ protocols)	OAEU server	No dissemination of internal developments	Internal exploitation as basis for product development and improvement
Upscale_SDS	SDS of products	OAEU		pdf	OAEU server	No dissemination of internal developments	Internal exploitation as basis for product development

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Upscale_Permit	Trial permit application in FR; DE; PL	OAEU		Excel	OAEU server	No dissemination of internal developments	Internal exploitation as basis for product development
Upscale_Solutions	Rovensa_Solutions fill in list WP1	OAEU		Excel	OAEU server	No dissemination of internal developments	Internal exploitation as basis for product development and improvement
MoA documentation (D2.2)	Mode of action described for novel SAGROPIA solutions	AIT	Lab testing, microscopy analysis, field testing	Text files supported by Excel spreadsheets and image files (....)	Server AIT; stored 5 years post project	Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications	To be shared for product exploitation; for further development, data for regulatory approvals and product improvement
Genome information and analysis of MO solutions (D2.2)	Genome analysis of microbial solutions	AIT	Lab analyses	Genebank and Fasta (text) files, raw sequence data, 15Gb; Text file reports	Server AIT; stored 5 years post project	Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications	To be shared for product exploitation; for further development, data for regulatory approvals and product improvement

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Molecular and gene expression studies on MoA	RNA expression data for biological solutions	AIT	Lab analyses	Raw sequence data, 200Gb; Spreadsheet and Text file reports	Server AIT; stored 5 years post project	Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications	To be shared for product exploitation; for further development, data for regulatory approvals and product improvement
TOX Dossier (D2.3)	Results of testing SAGROPIA solutions regarding potential risks and environmental toxicity	OAEU	Risk testing and analysis	Text file (report) and associated Excel spreadsheet with experimental data	OAEU server	not decided	not decided in detail depending on results of WP1 – essential data for regulatory approvals
WP3							
IPM Field testing 1 (D3.1)	Data derived from on field-evaluation (no 1) of IPM strategies	WBF-AGS	Literature review, expert interviews, field testing	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file	Server WBF-AGS stored 5 years post project; working versions on SAGROPIA share	All data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan	Specific data supporting for regulatory approvals and product improvement for SAGROPIA products

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IPM Field testing 2 (D3.2)	Data derived from on field-evaluation (no 2) of IPM strategies	WBF-AGS	Field testing	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file	Servers of partners for local trials; consolidated versions on WBS-AGS Server stored 5 years post project and SAGROPIA share	All data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan	To be updated after results of first year trials; specific data supporting for regulatory approvals and product improvement
IPM Field testing 3 (D3.1)	Data derived from on field-evaluation (no 3) of IPM strategies	WBF-AGS	Field testing	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file	Servers of partners for local trials; consolidated versions on WBS-AGS Server stored 5 years post project and SAGROPIA share	All data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan	To be updated after results of first and second year trials; specific data supporting for regulatory approvals and product improvement
WP4							
Field trials / 1st Season (D4.1)	Data from field trials performed in the first test season (2026)	SZ	Field testing	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file (Test report)		Data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan - to be defined in more detail after results of WP1 –3 are available in M20 onwards	Specific data supporting for regulatory approvals and product improvement for SAGROPIA products –to be defined in more detail after results of WP1 –3 are available in M20 onwards

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Field trials / 2nd Season (D4.2)	Data from field trials performed in the second test season (2027)	SZ	Field testing	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file (Test report)		Dissemination strategy updated in more detail after season 2026	Data needed for product development and regulatory approvals defined in more detail after season 2026
Field trials / 3rd Season (D4.3)	Data from field trials performed in the first test season (2028)	SZ	Field testing	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file (Test report)		Dissemination strategy updated in more detail after season 2026 and 2027	Data needed for product development and regulatory approvals defined in more detail after season 2026 and 2027
IPM Best Practice Guide (D4.4)	Recommendations for farmers on IPM best practice	SZ	Desk work	Guidance document, brochure		Dissemination in agricultural journals	Outputs feeding into policy
WP5							
Equivalency factors (D5.1)	Dataset of functional equivalency factors	AIT	Literature and Company data evaluation	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file	Server AIT; stored 5 years post project	Through seminars, international symposium and peer reviewed scientific publications	Basis for policy briefs D6.6, feeding into policy improvements-summing up policy-relevant results.

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<p>LCA Data (D5.2)</p>	<p>LCA data assessed across practices, including new impact pathways</p>	<p>DTU</p>	<p>Literature review and toxicity reports, Inventory databases, project partners</p>	<p>In digital form of quantitative type (Excel spreadsheet/Text file)</p>	<p>Network storage drive hosted at DTU stored for 10 years</p>	<p>All data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan</p>	<p>Leveraging output data across practices to improve sustainability performance, optimize resource efficiency, and drive innovation in product development and process optimization in organizations</p>
<p>Environmental sustainability (D5.3)</p>	<p>Data on absolute environmental sustainability performance</p>	<p>DTU</p>	<p>Literature review, inventory databases, project partners</p>	<p>In digital form of quantitative type (Excel spreadsheet/Text file)</p>	<p>Network storage drive hosted at DTU stored for 10 years</p>	<p>All data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan</p>	<p>Empowering organizations to set and achieve science-based targets, ensuring their operations align with planetary boundaries and contribute to long-term environmental stewardship, summing up policy relevant results</p>

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Socio-economic sustainability (D5.4)	Data on socio-economic sustainability & overall practices ranking	WBF-AGS	Literature review, project partners	Excel spreadsheet/ Text file	Server WBF-AGS stored 5 years post project; working versions on SAGROPIA share	All data will be disseminated through publishing in scientific journals, and relevant conferences and events as listed in DEC plan	Potential regulatory approvals and product development, policy briefs D6.6, summing up policy-relevant results
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